

S1 Detector chamber – InGaAs & InSb setup

5 Figure S1: Detector chamber of the FTIR. Yellow path shows the light source entering the chamber, split 50/50 by the CaF₂ beamsplitter (BS) and directed to the InGaAs and InSb detectors. A five-place filter wheel is exchanging the filter in front of the InSb according to the experiment. This five-place filter wheel holds four filters with one place open. An eight-place filter wheel holding two filters, with six open places is located before the detector chamber entrance. The filters' band frequencies (wavenumbers) are presented in Table 1 in the main paper.

S2 The Cyprus AirCores

S2.1 The AirCores sampling

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Figure S2: Photos from Nicosia, Cyprus AirCore campaign. A cross section of our AC sampling system (lower left) and the AC just launched (upper left). Here, we use a low-resolution AC device from LSCE built as a double stainless-steel, coated tubing of 35 m long, consisting of a 12 m long 8 mm in diameter tube and a 23 m long 4 mm in diameter tube. The vertical air samples were analysed with a cavity ring-down spectrometry (CRDS) gas analyzer by Picarro, model

15 G2401. Right: photo from the AC launch of 30 June 2020.

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Table S1: AirCore flights info

Flight	Date	Launch time (UTC)	Launch location Lat (°N), Lon (°E)	Recovery time (valve closing) (UTC)	Landing location Lat (°N), Lon (°E)	Landing location characterization	Balloon cutoff altitude (km)	Profile ceiling (km)	Profile floor (km)	Landing distance from FTS (km)
1	19-6-2020	09:05	35.01, 32.45	11:52	35.11, 33.34	Residential	33	22.86	0.83	5.5
2	29-6-2020	07:46	34.84, 32.87	10:30	35.05, 33.53	Rural	25	21.83	1.43	17
3	30-6-2020	08:40	34.84, 33.39	11:15	34.97, 33.39	Rural	30	23.10	1.11	20

Figure S3: AirCore (AC) flight trajectories and landing locations during the June 2020 campaign. The colored markers indicate the landing sites of each flight: blue for 19 June (Flight 1), orange for 29 June (Flight 2), and green for 30 June (Flight 3). The solid trajectories are colored by altitude (see color bar). The dashed lines of corresponding color show the azimuthal range of the TCCON FTS line of sight during each flight. For each color pair, the rightmost dashed line corresponds to the FTS viewing direction at the beginning of the AirCore descent, and the leftmost dashed line corresponds to the viewing direction at the time of landing. Map data from © OpenStreetMap contributors 2024. Distributed under the Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL) v1.0.

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NOAA HYSPLIT MODEL
 Backward trajectories ending at 0900 UTC 29 Jun 20
 GDAS Meteorological Data

Figure S4: Hysplit airmasses backtrajectories for the AirCore flight of 29 June, running 96 h backwards. Black star represents the location of TCCON Nicosia (Cyprus), where the airmasses (in red, blue and green) arrive on 29 June, at 1.5 km, 5.5 km and 13 km altitude respectively. The green airmass appears to be part of the Asian Summer Monsoon Anticyclone (ASMA), and it was above India 96 h before crossing over Cyprus.

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S2.2 FTS Xluft data during AC flights

45 **Figure S5:** $X_{\text{luf}}t$ time series during AC campaign (grey markers). $X_{\text{luf}}t$ flight medians in orange markers and red horizontal lines show the TCCON nominal values for $X_{\text{luf}}t$ median. This is a check that the $X_{\text{luf}}t$ flight median is within the median nominal values of 0.996 – 1.002.

S2.3 Constructing the lower and upper bounds of the AirCore profiles

```
# Calculate upper and lower bounds for each species (the AirCore uncertainty)
for specie in species:
    data['lower_alt_unc_lim_' + specie.lower()] = data['lower_alt_unc_lim_' + specie.lower()]/1000 #from m to km
    data['upper_alt_unc_lim_' + specie.lower()] = data['upper_alt_unc_lim_' + specie.lower()]/1000 #from m to km
    data[specie + '_lo'] = data[specie] - unc_values[specie]
    data[specie + '_up'] = data[specie] + unc_values[specie]
    data[specie + '_Alt_min'] = data['Alt'] - data['lower_alt_unc_lim_' + specie.lower()]
    data[specie + '_Alt_max'] = data['Alt'] + data['upper_alt_unc_lim_' + specie.lower()]

# Calculate bounded means for upper and lower bounds
data[specie + '_lo_bo'] = data['Alt'].apply(
    lambda x: np.nanmean(data[(x >= data[specie + "_Alt_min"]) & (x <= data["Alt"])][specie + '_lo']))
data[specie + '_up_bo'] = data['Alt'].apply(
    lambda x: np.nanmean(data[(x <= data[specie + "_Alt_max"]) & (x >= data["Alt"])][specie + '_up']))
```

50 **Figure S6:** Python snippet that constructs the lower and upper bounds of the main AirCore. It takes into account the in situ measurement uncertainty per gas specie (`unc_values[specie]`), which is 0.05 ppm, 0.7 ppb and 7 ppb for CO_2 , CH_4 and CO respectively, and the altitude uncertainty limits (`'lower_alt_unc_lim_gas_specie'` and `'upper_alt_unc_lim_gas_specie'`), as provided in the AirCore data files (<https://zenodo.org/records/13132338>, last access: 5 December 2024) for this type of AC sampling device. For each gas specie, two types for each of lower and upper bounds are constructed. The `'specie_lo'` and `'specie_lo_bo'` for the lower bounds, and the `'specie_up'` and `'specie_up_bo'` for the upper bounds. Then, these bounds are treated as extra AirCore profiles. We get the smallest value amongst the `'specie_lo'` and `'specie_lo_bo'` per altitude to construct the gas lower bound (`'gas_lower'`) and the largest amongst the `'specie_up'` and `'specie_up_bo'` to construct the gas upper bound (`'gas_upper'`). See example in Fig. S7.

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60 **Figure S7:** Left: An example of the bounds that result from the python code in Fig. S6 for CO for flight 1. Light blue marker indicates 'specie_lo' and blue marker indicates 'specie_lo_bo'. Pink marker indicates 'specie_up' and dark red indicates 'specie_up_bo'. Right: In order to have just one set of bounds, we selected the smallest value in 'specie_lo' and 'specie_lo_bo' at each altitude to create the gas lower bound ('CO_lower', blue), and similarly, to create the gas upper bound ('CO_upper', red), we selected the largest value in 'specie_up' and 'specie_up_bo' at each altitude.

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S2.4 Assembling full profiles

70 Figure S8: This figure shows a schematic of the approach followed to construct a full vertical profile. For comparability with the
 75 FTS prior, the in situ profile needs to extend from 0 m (a.s.l.) to 70 km. Both left and right panels show the same assembled profile
 (CO₂, 30 June flight); however, the left profile is in wet mole fractions and the right profile in dry mole fractions. Left (wet profile):
 Example of an assembled AirCore (AC) profile for the flight on 30 June, 2020, showing CO₂ in wet mole fractions. This vertical
 80 resolution profile, was used for the GGG2020 custom retrievals (see Sect. S2.5). Red stars represent the re-gridded AC profile, while
 a flat extrapolation of the lowest AC measurement to near-ground levels is shown as red crosses in the inset. The grey shading
 around the main AC profile indicates the uncertainty bounds; which is very small for CO₂. The FTS prior profile is depicted as grey
 circles connected by a grey line, with the prior used to extend the in situ profile upwards shown as grey circles connected by a red
 line. The horizontal dashed line marks the altitude of the last AC grid level. Near-surface in situ measurements are represented by
 the median (orange 'x') and the mean \pm standard deviation (green triangle). The inset focuses on the lower 3 km, showing near-
 surface variability and the comparability between the prior and in situ measurements. A complete profile is constructed by
 assembling 1) the re-gridded AC profile (red stars), 2) the FTS prior above the highest AC measurement (gray circles with red line),
 3) flat extrapolation of the lowest AC measurement to near-ground levels (red cross at 0.88 km), and 4) the in situ surface median
 (orange 'x') for the lowest two levels (0 and 0.42 km). Right (dry profile): Assembled AirCore profile in full resolution (in dry mole-
 fractions). This profile was used as the true profile, x , in Eq. 2, main paper. The \sim 8 ppm difference near the ground of the left- and

right-panel profiles is due to the difference between wet and dry mole fraction; which is largest at the surface due to the concentration of water there.

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S2.5 Running custom GGG2020 retrievals

We follow the method of Laughner et al. (2024) and run custom GGG2020 retrievals by replacing the GGG priors with the assembled AirCore profiles (see Fig. S8, left). Our method of re-gridding the AC profile to the FTS levels is simple (Fig. S8, left), unlike Laughner et al. (2024) that compute weighted averages of the in situ measurements around the adjacent FTS levels (see Sect. C3 and Fig. C1 of Laughner et al. (2024)). Another difference is that when running the GGG2020 custom retrievals, we do apply the in situ correction (AICF) on the custom X_{gas} data as post-processing. In addition, we use retrieved FTS data of spectra recorded within $\pm 1\text{h}$ around the AirCore central flight time instead of the AC landing time.

Table S2 summarizes the retrieval fitting errors of custom versus public data.

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Table S2: Mean fitting errors resulting from the fitting residuals (“xgas_error” variable in the public data), in “custom” vs. standard (public) data retrievals. Values are rounded to the nearest decimal.

Flight number	1	2	3
	Fitting error mean \pm STD		
custom.X _{CO₂} (ppm)	0.48 \pm 0.01	0.54 \pm 0.01	0.57 \pm 0.02
public.X _{CO₂}	0.45 \pm 0.01	0.50 \pm 0.01	0.51 \pm 0.01
custom.X _{CH₄} (ppb)	2.17 \pm 0.04	2.20 \pm 0.06	2.45 \pm 0.08
public.X _{CH₄}	2.02 \pm 0.08	2.52 \pm 0.06	2.33 \pm 0.05
custom.X _{CO} (ppb)	1.16 \pm 0.04	0.96 \pm 0.01	1.13 \pm 0.04
public.X _{CO}	1.22 \pm 0.03	0.99 \pm 0.02	1.13 \pm 0.04

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S2.6 X_{gas} and AC. X_{gas} uncertainty calculation

All types of measurements are susceptible to two main types of effects causing measurement uncertainty: random and systematic. Below we list uncertainty sources for both FTS-derived X_{gas} (valid for standard and custom retrieval) and AirCore (AC)-derived X_{gas} measurements.

105 [X_{gas}]: The FTS-derived dry-air mole fractions have two known sources of uncertainty described below.

1. Random effects; represented by the measurement variability within the selected flight window of ± 1 hour around the AirCore (AC) central time, quantified as the standard deviation around the mean ($\epsilon_{X_{\text{gas.std}}}$).

2. Systematic instrument effects; deviations in X_{luff} from the nominal network value (0.999) introduce bias in X_{gas} values. To account for this, we include an X_{luff} -derived bias ($\epsilon_{X_{\text{luff}}}$) using Eq. C11 and values in Table C6 from Laughner et al. (2024).

110 The total uncertainty is calculated by combining standard uncertainties (from random effects) in quadrature. Known systematic uncertainties (i.e. $\epsilon_{X_{\text{luff}}}$) are added separately, following Eq. 13 in Laughner et al. (2024), here Eq. S1:

$$\epsilon_{X_{\text{gas}}} = \sqrt{\epsilon_{X_{\text{gas.std}}}^2 + |\epsilon_{X_{\text{luff}}}|}, \quad (\text{S1})$$

Unknown systematic effects are those identified through comparisons with independent measurements, such as WMO-referenced in situ AC profiles. These effects are corrected network-wide using the in situ correction outlined in Sec. 8.3 of
115 Laughner et al. (2024).

[AC.X_{gas}]: For the integrated AC-derived total-column quantity (see Eq. 2, main paper), the primary sources of uncertainty arise from:

1. Unmeasured atmospheric sections (Geibel et al., 2012; Laughner et al., 2024; Messerschmidt et al., 2011; Wunch et al., 2010).

120 2. The AirCore measurements uncertainty.

The magnitude of these uncertainties is largely gas dependent. For point 1) we account for the unmeasured stratospheric and surface levels, and this calculation aims in assessing how the in situ integrated AC.X_{gas} will be affected by the assumptions made to extend it.

Given that our in situ profiles extend up to the lower stratosphere, the most significant unmeasured part is the upper
125 stratosphere. While Messerschmidt et al. (2011) accounted for ~ 2.02 ppm stratospheric uncertainty for AC.X_{CO₂} by not measuring any part of the stratosphere, our stratospheric uncertainty should be considerably less.

We quantify stratospheric uncertainty (ϵ_{strat}) following Sec. C6 of Laughner et al. (2024), by calculating the difference between a total column-integrated perturbed and unperturbed profile (see Eq. C10 in Laughner et al. (2024)). The perturbed profile is constructed by adding twice the difference between the top AC profile gas value measurement and the corresponding
130 FTS prior level (Eq. C9 in Laughner et al. (2024)). This difference between the AC and the prior value is shown in Fig. S8 (left) at the “cutoff altitude”.

For the lowest unmeasured section (typically the lowest 0-1500 m, or 1-3 FTS grid levels), we flat-extrapolate the last AC measurement down to 880 m (the 3rd GGG grid level). From the 880 m to the Nicosia FTS level (180 m) we assume the surface gas value has a range from the surface in situ (Picarro, 185 m ASL) mean \pm standard deviation, to the last AC measured value.

135 The total column-uncertainty due to this possible range (ϵ_{ground}) is calculated by integrating profiles where the lowest levels are filled once with the minimum and once with the maximum of this possible range.

AirCore measurements themselves entail uncertainty ($\epsilon_{\text{AirCore}}$) arising from the altitude measurement precision, gas mixing during sampling, and instrument precision.

The AC gas and altitude measurement uncertainties provided by LSCE/LMD are used to construct upper and lower profile bounds (see Sect. S2.3). These bounds (see Fig. S7, right) yield the AC uncertainty ($\epsilon_{\text{AirCore}}$) when we take the difference between the integrated upper and lower profile bounds, while keeping the unmeasured stratospheric and surface sections appended to the complete profile fixed.

The total uncertainty for AC.X_{gas}, incorporating both random ($\epsilon_{\text{AirCore}}$, ϵ_{ground}) and systematic (ϵ_{strat}) components, is calculated by Eq. S2 here, following Eq. C12 in Laughner et al., (2024):

$$\epsilon_{\text{AC.X}_{\text{gas}}} = \sqrt{\epsilon_{\text{AirCore}}^2 + \epsilon_{\text{ground}}^2} + |\epsilon_{\text{strat}}|, \quad (\text{S2})$$

Table S3: Uncertainty components for Nicosia retrieved X_{gas} (standard) per gas and per flight. Uncertainty sources are the $\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{gas, std}}}$, representing the measurement variability and $\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{lufft}}}$ the X_{lufft}-derived bias (see Sec. S2.6). The uncertainties for the custom-retrieved X_{gas} are not shown as the values are almost identical to the standard retrievals. Values are rounded to the nearest decimal.

X _{gas}	Flight 1	Flight 2	Flight 3
	$\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{gas, std}}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{lufft}}}$	$\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{gas, std}}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{lufft}}}$	$\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{gas, std}}}$, $\epsilon_{\text{X}_{\text{lufft}}}$
public.X_{CO₂} (ppm)	0.53, -0.07	0.47, -0.22	0.45, -0.16
public.X_{CH₄} (ppb)	2.2, -0.05	2.1, -0.17	2.5, -0.13
public.X_{CO} (ppb)	1.6, 0	1.2, 0	2.3, 0

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Table S4: Uncertainty components for Nicosia AC.X_{gas}. The ϵ -AirCore component represents the uncertainty in the integrated total column DMF, solely from the AC measurements. Similarly, the ϵ -ground represents the uncertainty in the integrated total column DMF caused by the possible range of values used to fill the near ground profile levels. The ϵ -strat represents the stratospheric uncertainty from the unmeasured part of the stratosphere, calculated as described in Sec. S2.6. Last column shows the mean uncertainty (\pm std) of all flights.

AC.X _{gas}	Uncertainty source	Flight 1	Flight 2	Flight 3	mean \pm std
AC.X _{CO₂} (ppm)	ϵ -strat ϵ -ground ϵ -AirCore	0.05	0.24	0.13	0.14 \pm 0.10
		0.02	0.20	0.02	0.08 \pm 0.10
		0.30	0.38	0.30	0.33 \pm 0.05
AC.X _{CH₄} (ppb)		10.1	9.5	1.9	7.2 \pm 4.6
		0.1	0.3	0.5	0.3 \pm 0.2
		10.2	7.5	7.7	8.5 \pm 1.5
AC.X _{CO} (ppb)		1.8	5.6	3.7	3.7 \pm 1.9
		0.3	0.3	1.2	0.6 \pm 0.5
		15.3	15.1	15.8	15.4 \pm 0.3

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S2.7 Case study: Spatial and temporal variability during “flight 2” – 29 June 2020

The 29 June flight exhibited a larger difference between the AirCore and retrieved XCO₂ values than the 19 June flight. This is a complex case that merits detailed discussion. The 30 June flight also showed a larger difference in XCO₂; we note that the 30 June flight exhibits similar characteristics to the 29 June case: (1) a near-surface enhancement (but smaller) around 1 km altitude captured by the AirCore, (2) a substantial drawdown in ground-based in situ measurements during the flight window, (3) a local meteorological shift, (4) a modest decrease in XCO later in the day, and (5) comparable geometric sampling differences between the FTS line-of-sight and AirCore trajectory. For brevity, we focus our detailed discussion on the 29 June flight, but the observations, analysis, and conclusions are largely transferable to 30 June. The relevant figures for both flights are provided here (Figs. S9-S13). In the following paragraphs, we discuss the various factors contributing to these larger differences in XCO₂.

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1) AirCore profile characteristics and ground-level data: On this flight, the AirCore measured a near-surface enhancement in CO₂ and CO around 1.4 km altitude (see Fig. 4 (a), (c), grey profiles; main paper), which was the AC's lowest measurement ('floor'). We used the ground-based in situ measurements at 185 m ASL to fill the missing values between 180-420 m (see Fig. S8 and Sect. S2.4). However, these ground-based measurements do not show a similar enhancement. On the contrary, there is a substantial drawdown in both CH₄ and CO after 08:00 UTC (see Fig. S9). This discrepancy between the ground-based in situ and the last AC measurement causes the large ground uncertainty (ϵ -ground) for flight 2: 0.20 ppm for AC.XCO₂ compared to only 0.02 ppm for flights 1 and 3 (Table S4). In general, all AC.XCO₂ uncertainties are larger for flight 2 compared to the other two flights, reflecting the greater ambiguity in constructing the full profile.

2) FTS observations during the flight window: The TCCON X_{gas} measurements during the AirCore flight window (± 1 hour around the central flight time) do not show any enhancement corresponding to the near-surface feature captured by the AirCore (see Fig. S10, '2020-06-29'). However, a slight enhancement is visible later in the day, between 12:00-13:00 UTC in both XCH₄ and XCO (see Fig. S10, '2020-06-29', (b2), (c2)), suggesting temporal evolution of the atmospheric state.

190 **Figure S9: Time series of CO₂ ((a1)-(a3)), CH₄ ((b1)-(b3)) and CO ((c1)-(c3)) in dry-air mole-fraction, measured by the ground-based Picarro G2401 during the three days of the AirCore flights. Red solid line indicates AirCore landing time and dashed lines the ± 1 h time window around AirCore central time. The gap in the measurements' time-series is due to the AirCore analysis.**

Figure S10: Time series of XCO₂ ((a1)-(a3)), XCH₄ ((b1)-(b3)) and XCO ((c1)-(c3)) measured by TCCON Nicosia during the three days of the AirCore flights. Red solid line indicates AirCore landing time and dashed lines the ± 1 h time window around AirCore central time.

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3) Meteorological analysis: To understand these observations, we examined the local meteorology during the flight using data from two sources: (1) the nearest Department of Meteorology station (Athalassa, station 1666, 35.15°N 33.4°E, 162 m ASL, ~1.5 km from the FTS), and (2) the meteorological station co-located with the Nicosia FTS (Fig. S11 and S12, respectively).

200 The data reveal a significant meteorological shift starting around 08:00 UTC:

- Wind direction changed from 270° (West) to 0°-45° (N-NNE) (Fig. S11 (b2))
- Relative humidity dropped substantially (Figs. S11 and S12, (c2)), and
- Mean wind speed increased (Fig. S11 and S12, (a2)).

205 This near-surface wind shift appears to have advected cleaner air toward the ground-based in situ site, as evidenced by the pronounced drawdown in CH₄ and CO after 08:00 UTC (Fig. S9 (b2), (c2)). This indicates that the enhancement observed by the AirCore was likely confined to an elevated layer between approximately 200 m and 2 km and was not well coupled to the boundary layer sampled at the surface.

It is also plausible that the cleaner air mass had not yet reached the AC landing location at the time of sampling. Because the ground-based in situ site (co-located with the TCCON instrument; see Fig. S3) is located north of the AC landing site, and the

210 wind shift was from the north, the cleaner air would be expected to arrive at the in situ station first, consistent with the observed timing.

215 **Figure S11: Time series of wind speed (WIND_SPEED, (a1)-(a3)), wind direction (WIND_DIR, (b1)-(b3)) and humidity (HUMIDITY, (c1)-(c3)) measured by the Athalassa meteo station in the forested park southeast of the Nicosia FTS (35.15°N 33.4°E, 162m asl) during the three days of the AirCore flights. There are no data recorded on 19 June 2020. Red solid line indicates AirCore landing time and dashed lines the ± 1 h time window around AirCore central time.**

220 **Figure S12: Time series of wind speed (WSPD, (a1)-(a3)), ambient pressure (POUT, (b1)-(b3)) and humidity (HOUT, (c1)-(c3)) measured by TCCON Nicosia meteo station during the three days of the AirCore flights. Red solid line indicates AirCore landing time and dashed lines the ± 1 h time window around AirCore central time.**

4) Spatial sampling mismatch: An additional complication arises from the geometric sampling differences between instruments. Near the AirCore landing time ($\sim 10:05$ UTC), the FTS line-of-sight (see Fig. S13, orange dashed lines) was markedly different from the AirCore trajectory (Fig. S13, AirCore ‘landing’ in orange marker). More specifically:

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- The solar azimuth angle was 190° - 195° (SSW direction), while the AirCore was heading eastward
 - The solar zenith angle was small ($\sim 12^\circ$) during landing, meaning the FTS was sampling high in the atmosphere
 - The AirCore trajectory: the AC descended from the West, heading to the East, passing under but laterally displaced from the FTS line-of-sight (see Fig. S3)

Therefore, it is reasonable to conclude that the two instruments sampled different air masses, particularly at lower altitudes where the horizontal gradients were likely strongest due to the meteorological transition.

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5) Limited improvement from custom retrievals: One might expect that replacing the GGG2020 priors with the true AirCore profiles in custom retrievals would yield custom. X_{gas} values much closer to AC. X_{gas} than the public. X_{gas} . However, this was not the case (see Table 2). Several factors explain this:

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- Partial profile replacement: we replace only three trace-gas profiles (CO₂, CH₄, and CO) while numerous other profiles – including H₂O, temperature, and pressure – remain unchanged
 - Re-gridding smoothing: re-gridding the high-resolution AirCore profiles to the coarser GGG grid levels reduces some of the profile variability
 - Spatial mismatch propagation: If the FTS and AirCore sampled air masses with genuinely different profiles, using the AirCore instead of the prior does not eliminate error from an incorrect prior shape

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Conclusion – Implications for comparison: given these considerations, we believe the disagreement on June 29 reflects genuine atmospheric heterogeneity and spatial sampling differences rather than systematic instrumental biases. The fact that:

1) flight 1 shows good agreement for XCO₂ while flights 2 and 3 present similarly complex cases (Table 2),

2) the disagreement on flight 2 falls within the combined uncertainties when the individual uncertainties are properly accounted for (all larger in flight 2 compared to flights 1 and 3, see Table S4 for XCO₂),

245 3) the custom retrieval does not improve agreement (supporting the spatial mismatch hypothesis);

support the interpretation that this case demonstrates the challenges of comparing column and in situ measurements in spatially heterogeneous conditions, rather than indicating a systematic problem with the TCCON Nicosia data.

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